

IN UZBEKISTAN, THE LIBRARY OF HISTORY

(1945-1955 YEARS)

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ABSTRACT

In this article, especially in the first years of independence, currently in our country young generation of spiritual and intellectual potential, elevate the mind and outlook thought, love and loyalty to the people of the motherland and the perfect person to live with a sense of nurturing, aimed at improving the culture of the readers who have an important role in wide-ranging implementation of reforms in Uzbekistan in the years after the war and marksizm-leninizm consists of the general library on the basis of the outlook out of business, development and the ideology of the period in the library arises from the requirements of, the people of Uzbekistan national traditions to see confirmation propaganda work identifies issues such as the implementation of.

INTRODUCTION. Today the head of state Shavkat Mirziyoev noble values and traditions in the life of society to conduct deep to find a resolution, in particular, our people, particularly the spiritual and intellectual potential of the younger generation in mind, elevate thought and outlook, and love of the motherland and loyalty to the people who live with a sense of nurturing, is the perfect person an important role in the culture of the readers who have a particular focus, 2017 and January of this year, on September 13, a 13-year "Book publication and distribution of the product of the system development to promote and enhance the culture of the readers read the book and on the

application of complex measures on[1]to the edge of reader interaction, and promotingthe commission on the conclusion of the drinkamong local governments in each district and the city to place orders and trade store that specializes in the organization of the book, a legal entity in order to support them in the status of state property free of unused objects useful to business entities will be put to anish, to ensure the formation of their material and technical base, and most importantly a place in a modern-type is envisaged the establishment of book stores.

Also, the organization of meaningful leisure time of young people in the year 2019 the purpose of the march 19 "5

important initiative" program, [2] also in that the initiative was put forward of the formation of the culture of the young readers.

THE MAIN PART. If you look into the history of middle-sof the state over "when we look at the national transforming" the so-called culture, marksizm-leninizm consists of the general outlook on it to the phenomena of social life sinfiy approach to partiyaviylik and the principle of popular leninchasauce developed in its main metodido sosialistik is realism. The population taken in the program of the cpsu a number of "enlightenment" in the implementation of the functionsat pre-school education schools, secondary special and higher education systemin addition to an, cultural, educational and spiritual education institutions, the network of libraries, clubs, cinemas before the teamsresponsible put in a request, and cultural and educational activity of the communist partiya of materials has become an integral part. Cultural and educational institutions of the ruling party, the unitswhich conducted and propaganda are powerful weapons as wide masses into the minds of the new ideology serves to implant.

In the years after the war the soviet system was implemented in Uzbekistan in the context of existing libraries of their activities, educational work in order to expand and improve on various topics, book exhibitions, lectures, discussions, became one of the principal organizers of the conference and organized the night. Cultural-educational institutions, including the head of the state for strengthening of the library, much of the full year to meet the growing demand of the population in

1945 with the decision of the council of people's commissioners of the USSR in the Republic ally, in particular, the work of the committee on cultural and educational institutions of Uzbekistan and their local authorities Uzbekistan SSR also regional, city and district cultural and educational work of the department was established. [3:85]

In the years after the war, the government of Uzbekistan that out among the masses propaganda to raise levels of committed work, how to boost aimed at the activities of cultural and educational institutions made a decision.

In particular, the Republic of Uzbekistan on march 12 1946, Central committee and Mini Uzbekistan SSR and soviet str "Uzbekistan SSR cultural and educational institutions truston measures to improve" the decision, which a number of measures to implement the approved plans. [4:108]

The implementation of this decision will go to existing cultural and educational institutions in Uzbekistan, life, mind your own business, including the expansion of the circle staged, cultural and educational institutions, which is one of the more books your library is filled to organize and fund a certain portion of the agricultural literature, this bookincreased the number of er.

For example, in 1946 on the territory of Uzbekistan of books in the library 11,5% to the political-social sector of the literature of the organization, in the year of 1955 that number 13,7 % was by. The literature in the natural sciences, which in turn guides 3.1%, from 2,9%and decreased by. [5:276] in stock the library kept a large part of the book (60-70%) was

in the Russian language is a form of literature. Nevertheless, collective farms and state farms of the population of Uzbekistan living in 95 to 96% was accounted for the representatives of the nation that makes local. [6:151] Additionally, there was the problem of the new library is also providing different levels in literature. The book is kept in stock large parts of the literature on the political-ideological character of the organization in the game, they basically propaganda to promote the party and the soviet state policy and was dedicated.

The library conducted among the population of the Republic political-educational work of diverse forms, methods of use, which is due to the destruction of war took a direct part in the economic recovery of the nation.

In the library of the Republic of agronomic, natural-scientific knowledge to promote comprehensive, meetings, conversations, lectures, organized the exhibition with the theme, by way of advanced agricultural vitrinalar the organization of experience.

In 1948, the library, the staff atk-bee the Republic of you is of great importance. Government bodies in the work of the council staff, writers, scientists, publishing, the book trade was attended by representatives of the organization and others.

The initial conclusions of the council of the network of the results of the recovery in the library of the library to the main tasks in bringing up young people did not put forward the nearest prospects have been identified. To attract a wide range of scientific and methodical work quite recommended guide necessary to improve

the production of the ministry in the activities of scientific libraries in the Republic of finish each other's work and the necessity to repeat was showing.[7:86]

The decision of the council of the Republic and has helped revive the work of the library of raising. A while in the library is named after Navoi organized for me to be methodical. Also to promote the synthesis of the target readers and servicing to advanced methods of in Uzbekistan is to improve the work of all libraries was.

Uzbekistan SSR of the soviet ministerial November 17, 1948, adopted on "Uzbekistan on measures to improve the work of the library" the decree of the library in the Republic of the material-technical base, strengthening, it is not based on issues such as the development of national traditions, but the party of the ideological-political ideology of the promotion of the functions were identified. In the decision between the population, mainly, the prime task was set to strengthen political and ateizm an education. Accordingly, the main content of the struggle against the religion of the work of the library of the past "harmful the world" to the prosecutor of the party and the soviet state issues, respectively.[8:108]

This in addition to this decision, until 1 January of the year in 1949, the public library of the network of full-establish the organization, is the appropriate distribution for buildings to do this to them. The necessary mass-political literature for the purchase of the library of every month the financial organs depending on the type of funds that distinguish them it was necessary.[9:86]

In order to ensure the implementation of this resolution in many regions of the Uzbekistan SSR in the library of the institution are allocated to buildings, although the library system to, no one to have handy in the building work.

In the library, not the way to grow the number of paid attention to the quality of the work. The confirmation of the lifestyle of this case can be seen from the following table.

**Number of libraries in Uzbekistan
(1940-1960 supports.) [10:151]**

Libraries the number of	the year		
	1940	1950	1960
	1792 units	1527 units	3317 units

The number of libraries's go that may have increased their personnel and provide training of operating personnel the task of the Uzbekistan SSR of the soviet ministerial year on June 2 1951 "Uzbekistan SSR measures to improve the work of the library of Uzbekistan "on the decree bring myself to accept. In this decision is that many in the region is at a low level of this population to the library-it was noted to show the negative effects of providing library service.[11:33] culture of the Republic this decision is married in order to implement the collective at the expense of collective funds for the preparation of the library staff from the production of dealing with divorce two months of the course of Tashkent city was founded. All of the Republic in regions librarian being called with the queue, was the increase of qualification.

10 may 1952, Uzbekistan april: (b) the bureau of the central committee "on the work of the club and the rural library" adopted a resolution. This decision was to establish the necessity of showing professional employees of the library in rural areas. Accordingly, Uzbekistan SSR, according to the guidelines of the department of cultural and educational

institutions, and in the year of 1954-1955 the regional library in the Republic the first of the year in more than 60 seminars held at different levels. This seminar while their turn in 600 to close librarian the staff grab. [12:86]

In 1953, the union and the organization of ministries of culture of the Republic of the book the book trade and library complex issues that are associated with the coordination and distribution through the network in a way will allow you to solve. The head of the ministry of culture in relation to the network library to the task were awarded. This state of the library the event also gave the opportunity to perform in the field of construction of centralized.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS. The side of the soviet government to improve the work of the library of performing directed the event despite their bird activitiesto improve to achieve lekarzem. But, 1950 inilsatn gradually starting a new collective farms and state farms in the organization of library available in the network of libraries of stock expansion and provide services to readers and the book begins to be introduced to the use of all the population.

According to the regulations adopted in the soviet state, 800 people to the readers on the library 1 coming was planned. Nevertheless, in the 1950s, in the middle of the Republic, the territory of the ida in the district of readers 4500 from one of the library it is.[13:276] in this situation, the soviet government of Uzbekistan's cultural and educational institutions. How to connection level is a clear example.

CONCLUSION. Conclusion I say, in the first years after the war the work of the library offering the further development of Uzbekistan adopted a number of important decisions. The main function of the library as seen in this period all the measures of deepening the content of the work, public service, and in particular with a number of services to launch, to give serious attention to improve the condition of the book stock of the library, the library was giving serious attention to the social and political life

connected with it. Independent libraries for the purpose of attracting new employees to help you get the knowledge of organs of the people of their resources a lot of work for implementation of the plan of assistance are carried out. The work of the library of large and complex problems that must be completed in the period after the war was necessary to raise the level of scientific and methodological guidance of the library of the Republic requires the consolidation point at a certain level.

1945-1955 years Uzbekistan sat the activity, who conducted the improve the work of the library book stock breeding in the field of a number of measures were identified. But, at the time level requirements, creating the conditions of possibility of this library from the requirements of the ideology of the period rda arises, the people of Uzbekistan national traditions to see whole sale propagation work performed.

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